

Multi-band Series-Fed Millimeter Wave Array Antenna with LP and CP Characteristics for 5G Applications

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(Received August 06, 2024; Revised April 16, 2025; Accepted April 17, 2025)

Abstract: The article presents the multi-band, left-hand circular polarized antenna array for millimeter-wave applications. The single radiating element has an orthogonal feed configuration from the single port. Thus, by adjusting the length of the orthogonal feed equal to $\lambda_1/2$ at 28 GHz, an approximately 150° phase difference between the two points is achieved. As a result, a left-hand circular polarization is achieved. Further, the bandwidth and radiation pattern are improved by arranging the radiating element along the one-dimension array (in the y-axis) and feeding it in series at the center. This is to achieve maximum antenna efficiency and reduce the losses. Consequently, penta resonances are generated at 27, 28, 31.5, 34.25, and 37.2 GHz with decent bandwidths of $|S_{11}| \geq 10$ dB are 26.7-26.95, 27.31-30.1, 31.18-31.65, 34.2-34.4, 37.2-37.85 GHz. The array antenna has resulted in circular polarization (CP) at 28 and 37.5 GHz and linear polarization (LP) at other bands. The achieved radiation is a narrow beam in a broadside direction with a half-power beamwidth of $< 12^\circ$ in YZ-plane. The antenna LP gain ranges from 12 to 14.4 dBi in the band of interest.

Keywords: 5G; array antenna; millimeter wave; multi-band; narrow beam; series-fed

1. Introduction

The data explosion from social media, parallel development of smart devices, IoTs, automated vehicles, and industrial applications demand higher data in the present era. The transition from sub-6 GHz to millimeter wave (mmWave) fulfills the required demand, offering wider bandwidth with low latency^{1,2}. However, the attenuation of the signal at mmWave drastically increases with the distance due to higher path loss exponent and the gaseous absorption in the atmosphere^{3,4}. Some applications working at mmWave, such as cellular^{5,6}, radar^{7,8}, advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS)^{6,9,10}, and satellite¹¹⁻¹⁴, require long-range communication. This leaves us with the challenge of designing the system to overcome the high path loss. One possible solution to this issue is to design narrow-beam antennas¹⁵. Thus, it can be accomplished through an array antenna¹⁶. Another possible solution is to design a lens antenna such as the Luneburg lens¹⁷. In an array antenna, the arrangement of

radiating elements (in 1D or 2D space) and the feeding network¹⁸⁻²⁰ (series, parallel, and hybrid) define its characteristics in terms of bandwidth, gain, and pattern formed. In²¹, non-uniform shape dielectric slabs are 3D printed, which are non-uniformly separated to control the phase difference in the y-axis, thus generating a narrow beam in the XZ plane and a wider beam in the YZ plane. In²², a microwave and mmWave dual-band operation with a narrow beam is achieved through a leaky wave antenna. Here, the microstrip patch elements of two types are arranged in series and fed by the microstrip line. Below this layer is a gap waveguide with another layer of slotted metal. Thus, it constitutes a multi-layer structure. The above-discussed antennas are large and multi-layer structures. Thus, in²³, a single-layer patch antenna with sets of parasitic elements is proposed. Due to parasitic elements, bandwidth improvement is observed. Such structure is replicated to a 1×4 array. However, these arrays are fed by a commercial Beambox network, which makes the design expensive. In²⁴, a planar beamforming

network is proposed for a series-fed array antenna. It adopted a two unequal transmission line concept, to which four ports are connected to control the phase for beam scanning. However, the geometry of the antenna is complex and multilayered.

Further, in ²⁵⁾, a Bezier curved dipole antenna is proposed, which is expanded to a 1×4 array. A corporate feed is adopted to feed the signal, through which equal power and phase are provided. Due to the dipole configuration, the antenna achieves end-fire radiation with a narrow beam. In ²⁶⁾, a series of split ring resonators are used, which are electromagnetically coupled through a microstrip line. Additional electromagnetic band-gap (EBG) metasurface has achieved a highly directional beam with suppressed side-lobe levels (SLL). With a binomial feeding to a non-uniform shape in ²⁷⁾, a low SLL is achieved. This work is extended in ²⁸⁾, where series of non-uniform shaped elements are extended in 2D space with binomial and tapered feed line, achieving wider bandwidth and narrow beam. In ²⁹⁾, a hybrid feed technique is used for a co-planar waveguide antenna. However, the obtained radiation pattern high SLL.

The above antennas are linearly polarized and require correct alignment to avoid losses. Also, these antennas are not very effective in multipath propagation. As a result, in ³⁰⁾, a circularly polarized antenna is proposed. The radiating elements are in series connected to a microstrip line forming leaky-wave antennas. It is fed by a pillbox reflector beamforming network to achieve right-hand and left-hand circular polarization. This feed mechanism makes the structure complex. A planar structure with series of circular patches arranged in spirical form are fed by an electromagnetically coupled microstrip line in ³¹⁾. However, the design is complex to realize. In, ³²⁻³⁴⁾, these designs presented the techniques for multi-band resonances.

Therefore, this article proposes a circularly polarized multi-band array antenna offering a lower complexity structure with a small form factor. The single-element is a conventional circular patch with a semi-circular slot in the radiator. An additional feed line of $\lambda_1/2$ (at 28 GHz) is connected orthogonally from the main feed of the patch to achieve dual excitation, consequently generating circular polarization. Further, the antenna is expanded to an array of eight elements fed by a microstrip feed line in a series fashion. The series feed at the center overcomes the limitation of feed line losses, and narrow bandwidth occurs in corporate and series end-feed ¹⁶⁾. Also, with this feed mechanism, the required phase difference is achieved, improving impedance matching and consequently achieving wider bandwidth.

2. Single-Element Antenna

The single-element antenna is a modified conventional

circular patch designed on Rogers 5880 substrate. The bottom of the substrate retains a full ground plane. The substrate permittivity, loss tangent, and thickness (h) are 2.2, 0.0009, and 0.254 mm. The antenna is designed and analyzed using the CST simulation software by adopting hexahedral meshing. The antenna is designed in three stages. In the first stage (Ant1), the dimensions of the circular patch are derived from the equations (1) to (2) ³⁵⁾:

$$f_0 = \frac{1.8412 v_0}{2\pi r_e \sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (1)$$

$$r_e = r \left\{ 1 + \frac{2h}{\pi r \epsilon_r} \left[\ln \left(\frac{\pi r}{2h} \right) + 1.7726 \right] \right\}^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

where, v_0 is speed of light in free space, r_e is the effective radius of the patch, r is the actual radius, and ϵ_r is the relative permittivity.

(a)

Fig. 1: Antenna evolution stages. (a) Ant1, (b) Ant2, and (c) Ant3 (proposed)

The antenna is fed by a microstrip line with an impedance Z_1 of 50Ω , as shown in Figure 1(a). The impedance matching of Ant1 is very poor, as shown in Figure 2. Further, in the second stage (Ant2), a portion of the signal is fed orthogonally by a $\lambda_1/2$ long feed line from the main microstrip feed line, as shown in Figure 1(b). Point P1 is the main feed point, and point P2 is the auxiliary feed point to the patch.

Fig. 2: (a) Reflection co-efficient $|S_{11}|$ of antenna stages. (b) Axial ratio representation of Ant3 antenna

Fig. 3: Surface current at varied angles/phase at 28 GHz. (a) 0° , (b) 40° , (c) 90° and (d) 170°

Fig. 4: Dimensions of the proposed Ant3 represented in mm are as follows: FL and FW are 2.35 and 0.78, SL is 1.8, R1 to R5 are 2.2, 1.44, 1.8, 2.8, and 3.2

Fig. 5: Radiation pattern of Ant3 at 28 GHz, demonstrating LHCP in XZ- and YZ-plane

Fig. 6: Simulated gain and total efficiency plot of Ant3

This feeding mechanism and adjusting the phase

difference between the two points to zero can achieve circular polarization. In our case, the phase difference between P1 and P2 is approximately 150° . The impedance matching at this stage has been slightly improved at 28 GHz. In the final stage (Ant3), a semi-circular slot is introduced in the patch to improve the impedance matching. As a result, a multi-band resonance occurred at around 28 GHz, as demonstrated in Figure 2(a). Also, due to the dual-feed mechanism, left-hand circular polarization (LHCP) is achieved with a 3 dB axial ratio, as displayed in Figure 2(b). However, the achieved 3 dB axial ratio is narrow from 27.67-27.85 GHz. To demonstrate the LHCP, the flow of surface current at varied phases is shown in Figure 3.

The relation of surface current (J_s) and far-field electric field (E) are related by equation (3) ³⁶.

$$E = \int_{Surface} \frac{-j\omega\mu e^{-jkd}}{4\pi d} J_s ds \quad (3)$$

where k is the wavenumber and d is the far-field distance. The dimensions of Ant3 are shown in Figure 4. The antenna demonstrates an LHCP gain of 4 dBic, and its radiation pattern is shown in Figure 5. The gain in dB and total efficiency over the large frequency range is shown in Figure 6.

To improve the impedance matching and axial ratio bandwidth, the Ant3 antenna is expanded to an array fashion; also, by adopting a series feed at the center, the required phase difference for CP is achieved.

3. Optimization of Ant3

The optimization process is to fine-tune the antenna performance of a single-element (Ant3) and to comprehend its performance for the variation in the structural dimensions. There are several methods to study the structure behavior for its change; for example, the characteristic mode theory (CMT) is a well-known method to suppress or excite the given mode through which the structure is optimized, as discussed in ^{37,38}. The alternative method is to apply an algorithm or theorem, such as a convolution neural network ³⁹ or ⁴⁰. However, we chose to perform the parametric sweep technique, which gives freedom in the range of variables; at the same time, the combination of variations is a time-consuming process. As a result, three parameters (SL, R1, and R4) are individually varied to validate their impact on impedance matching, reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$, and resonance frequency.

3.1. Parameter SL

3.2. Here, the parameter SL controls the arc length of the structure. The SL is the length from the top center of the circular patch to the upper semi-circular arc. It is varied from 1 mm to 2.6 mm with a step size of 0.2 mm. Figure 7(a) analysis indicates that only the optimum arc length could improve the impedance matching at 28 GHz. The shorter or longer arc length will cause poor impedance matching.

3.3. Parameter R1

3.4. The parameter R1 is the radius of the circular patch, it has a direct correlation with the resonance. The smaller the radius, the smaller will be the conductive area, thus resulting in higher resonance. On the other hand, a larger radius increases the patch area, thereby lowering the resonance. The parametric results in Figure 7(b) clearly validate the above analysis.

3.5. Parameter R4

The parameter R4 defines the thickness of the auxiliary feed line. Here, the R4 varies from 2.4 mm to 3 mm with an interval of 0.2 mm. The results in Figure 7(c) indicate that the thinner the auxiliary feed line, the dual-resonances are separated apart. However, for thicker auxiliary feed, it resulted in a single resonance at 28 GHz.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7: Parametric analysis of single-element antenna (Ant3) and its effect on reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$ for the variables (a) SL, (b) R1, and (c) R4

4. Series-Fed Array Antenna

The most adapted feeding techniques in the array antennas are parallel and series feed. The parallel (corporate) feed is easy to adopt and gives all the radiating elements equal power. However, it significantly suffers from radiation and ohmic losses. One of the possible solutions is to design the feed network with a groove-gap-waveguide [41]. However, it makes the structure complex. Thus, a series-fed technique has been adopted. In the series-fed mechanism, most of the power is radiated by the first few elements, and less power is propagated to the last element. If the residual power is not radiated from the n th elements, it causes reflections and affects the antenna radiation efficiency. So, the center-feed technique is more appropriate in series feed to obtain broadside radiation and better antenna efficiency [16,42]. Therefore, the above single-element antenna (Ant3) is arranged in series with eight elements and fed in series. The center-feed technique is adopted, as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8: Proposed center feed, series-fed excitation one-dimensional array

The antenna elements are uniform-shape and uniform-spacing, generating low-side lobe levels. The element-to-element (E_d) spacing is approximately $\lambda_1/2$ (at 28 GHz) to avoid the grating lobes. A quarter-wave transform is used to match the impedance (Z_1) of the 50Ω feed line to that of the radiating elements. The impedance of Z_2 and Z_3 is 70.7Ω and 100Ω , respectively. Due to the center-feed, the power between ports 2 and 6 is divided equally by half to 0.5 watts. Subsequently, the power for ports 3 to 5 is reduced from 0.25 to 0.1 watt, as shown in Figure 9. Similarly, the power at the right side to the center excitation can be seen.

Fig. 9: Power distribution in the proposed array antenna (Ant4)

The power distribution in the proposed array Ant4 follows the tapered amplitude distribution, and the excitation coefficient can be generalized as,

$$I_n = 2^{-(n-1)} ; \text{ for left elements} \quad (4)$$

where $n = 2, 3, 4,$ and 5 . Likewise,

$$I_n = 2^{-(n-5)} ; \text{ for right elements} \quad (5)$$

where $n = 6, 7, 8,$ and 9 . Generally, the array factor for a linear array is given by,

$$AF(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^N I_n e^{jkEd \cdot \cos\theta} \quad (6)$$

where k is the wavenumber, which is $2\pi/\lambda_1$.

For our tapered amplitude excitation case,

$$AF(\theta) = \sum_{n=2}^5 2^{-(n-1)} e^{jkEd(5-n) \cdot \cos(\theta)} + \sum_{n=6}^9 2^{-(n-5)} e^{jkEd(n-9) \cdot \cos(\theta)} \quad (7)$$

Solving for the above equation results in

$$AF(\theta) = 2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \cos(3kEd \cdot \cos(\theta)) + \frac{1}{4} \cos(3kEd \cdot \cos(\theta)) + \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{1}{8} \cos(3kEd \cdot \cos(\theta)) + \frac{1}{16} \right] \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) indicates the array factor for the tapered four elements on the left and the other four on the right side. The gain of the linear array antenna is a sum of the gain of Ant3 and the log of the number of elements.

$$G_{Array_Total} = G_{Ant3} + 10 \log_{10}(8) \quad (9)$$

Since the tapered amplitude excitation is applied to the array antenna, the gain of each element is not uniform. As a result, the gain of the array will be reduced to,

$$G_{Array_Total} = 10 \log_{10}(8) \quad (10)$$

Due to tapered amplitude distribution, the Ant4 has resulted in the generation of multi-band with bandwidth ranging from 26.84-27.4, 28-30.29, 31.38-31.75, and 37-37.53 GHz, as shown in Figure 10(a). Also, the achieved axial ratio (AR) bandwidth at 3 dB is 26.46-26.61 GHz and 37-37.5 GHz. Due to center-feed, the power is equally divided into elements 2 and 6 and reduces as it flows down the end element. As a result, at lower frequencies, say 27 and 28 GHz, a dual split beam is formed. However, at 31.5 GHz and above, a single narrow beam is formed. The impedances at the resonance bands are close to 50Ω with negligible reactance, as illustrated in Figure 10(b).

Fig. 10: (a) Simulated reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$ of Ant4.
 (b) Impedance characteristics of Ant4 over the large frequency range

The AR characteristics of Ant4 can be better comprehended by analyzing the counterplot at the resonance of 27 GHz, 28 GHz, 31.5 GHz, and 37.2 GHz, as illustrated in Figure 11. At 27 GHz and 31.5 GHz, the CP characteristics are not in the broadside, however, at some angle of $\theta = \pm 60^\circ$ and varied $\phi = 45^\circ, 60^\circ$, and so on. On the other hand, at 28 GHz, the axial ratio is < 3 dB for θ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ and also at different angles. At 37.2 GHz, the Ant4 has $\text{AR} < 3$ dB for $\theta = \pm 10^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ and 90° . Consequently, the CP radiation pattern is presented only for 28 GHz and 37.2 GHz in Figure 12, where the results indicate that at 28 GHz, dual narrow beams are formed with LHCP characteristics in the YZ-plane and wide beams in the XZ-plane. Likewise, at 37.2 GHz, a dual beam in the XZ-plane and a narrow beam in the YZ-plane are formed.

Fig. 11: Axial ratio counterplot for varied theta and phi at (a) 27 GHz, (b) 28 GHz, (c) 31.5 GHz, and (d) 37.2 GHz

Fig. 12: A CP radiation pattern of Ant4 at (a) 28 GHz and (b) 37.2 GHz

On the other hand, at 27 GHz and 31.5 GHz, the radiation is on the broadside with linear polarization; consequently, its radiation characteristics are shown in Figure 13. At 27 GHz, the antenna half-power beamwidth (HPBW) in the

XZ-plane is 49° with X-polarization level of -17 dB. In the YZ-plane, the dual split beams are formed with HPBW of 11.82° with X-polarization of -10 dB. At another frequency, that at 31.5 GHz, the Ant4 has resulted in a wide beam in the XZ-plane with HPBW of 56° and X-polarization of -25 dB. The YZ-plane resulted in a narrow beam with HPBW of 09° and X-polarization of -13.5 dB. The antenna has also achieved a maximum gain of 14 dB and a total efficiency $> 80\%$ in the band of interest, as illustrated in Figure 14.

Fig. 13: An LP radiation pattern of Ant4 at (a) 27 GHz and (b) 31.5 GHz

Fig. 14: Simulated gain and total efficiency of Ant4

5. Results and Discussion

The above single-element (Ant3) has a very narrow bandwidth ranging from 27.25-27.60 and 28.47-29.16 GHz, as shown in Figure 2. The corresponding axial ratio has resulted from 27.67-27.85 GHz, with LHCP radiation characteristics. The single-element antenna is arranged in a one-dimensional linear array along the y-axis and fed in series from the center to enhance the antenna performance. Due to the center feed, the array antenna has resulted in a tapered amplitude feed; consequently, low amplitude is supplied to the end element. This aids in reducing the side lobe levels and getting better directivity. The simulated results are validated by prototype fabricating the array antenna Ant4, as shown in Figure 15, and the respective measurement setup is demonstrated in Figure 16.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 15: Prototype fabricated array antenna Ant4. (a) Top view, (b) bottom view

Fig. 16: Measurement setup of (a) reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$ and (b) radiation pattern in anechoic chamber

The simulation results of the proposed Ant4 has resulted in five resonances at 27 GHz, 28.5 GHz, 31.5 GHz, 34.25 GHz, and 37.2 GHz, with its bandwidth at $|S_{11}| \geq 10$ dB are, 26.8-27.4 GHz, 28-30.25 GHz, 31.35-31.75 GHz, 34.22-34.33 GHz, and 36.98-37.45 GHz. The measured results also illustrate five resonances with bandwidth $|S_{11}| \geq 10$ dB are, 26.7-26.95 GHz, 27.31-30.1 GHz, 31.18-31.65 GHz, 34.2-34.4 GHz, and 37.2-37.85 GHz, as depicted in Figure 17(a). Ant4 also possesses the characteristics of CP at 28 GHz and 37.2 GHz, with its radiation on the broadside at $\theta = \phi = 0^\circ$. However, at 27 GHz, it is at different angles of θ and ϕ . Overall, the simulated 3 dB axial ratio are 26.45-26.62 GHz, 27-96-

28.05 GHz, and 37-37.5 GHz; and the measured is 26.2-26.8 GHz, 27.8-28.1 GHz, and 36.5-37.7 GHz, respectively, as illustrated in Figure 17(b).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 17: Simulated and measured (a) reflection coefficient $|S_{11}|$ and (b) axial ratio of Ant4

Consequently, the CP radiation pattern at 28 GHz and 37.2 GHz is shown in Figure 18. At 28 GHz, the simulated and measured results indicate an LHCP pattern with wide beam and RHCP of -13 dB. However, the YZ-plane resulted in a dual split beam with HPBW of 11° with SLL of -8 dB and X-polarization of -11 dB. Likewise, at 37.2 GHz, the XZ-plane has an LHCP wide beam with an X-polarization of -5 dB. The YZ-plane resulted in a narrow beam of 06° with an SLL and X-polarization of -8 dB.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(b)

Fig. 18: Simulated and measured CP radiation pattern at (a) and (b) 28 GHz. (c) and (d) at 37.2 GHz

At the other bands, the Ant4 has resulted in linear polarization (LP) at 27 GHz and 31.5 GHz, and its respective patterns are displayed in Figure 19. Here, as well, the XZ-plane has wide beam at 27 GHz with better X-polarization of 20 dB. The YZ-plane has a dual beam with HPBW of 12° and excellent SLL of -22 dB with X-polarization of -10 dB. Similarly, at 31.5 GHz, the XZ-plane has a wide beam with an X-polarization of -26 dB. The YZ-plane has a single beam at theta = 0° with HPBW of 08°, SLL of -13 dB, and X-polarization of -20 dB.

(c)

(a)

(d)

Fig. 19: Simulated and measured LP radiation pattern at (a) and (b) 27 GHz. (c) and (d) at 31.5 GHz

Fig. 20: Simulated and measured gain of Ant4 with simulated total efficiency

The Ant4 has resulted in a good gain in the 12 to 14.4 dBi range with a total efficiency of > 80 %, as illustrated in Figure 20. The antenna also demonstrated good front-to-back ratio radiation characteristics, as depicted in Figure

21.

Fig. 21: Simulated and measured front-to-back ratio of array antenna Ant4.

Table 1: Comparison of the proposed antenna with state-of-the-art designs

Ref.	Dim. mm ²	Res.	Ant. Type	BW (GHz)	Gain (dBi)	Radiation
³²⁾	NA	39/58/81	Parallel fed – Planar array	39.5-39.8/ 56-59/80-81.5	4/5	LP
³³⁾	12 × 3	28/38	Planar patch	27.96-28.64/ 37.54-38.4	6.11/7.15	LP
³⁴⁾	14 × 14	22.5/ 28/ 41.5/ 51/ 65	Monopole	22.4-23.7/ 26.68-30.35/ 38.1-43.46/ 57.63-67.85	4/ 5.3/ 5.8/ 8/ 7.2	LP
⁴³⁾	21 × 40	28	Series Fed – Planar array	27-28.4	11.7	LP
⁴⁴⁾	26 × 57	25	Parallel-fed – Dipole array	23-32	12.4	LP
Prop.	10 × 49.5	27/ 28/ 31.5/ 34.25/ 37.2	Series center fed – planar array	26.7-26.95/ 27.31-30.1/ 31.18-31.65/ 34.2-34.4/ 37.2-37.85	12/ 10/ 14.4/ 12.5/ 14	LP/ CP

6. Comparative Analysis

The performance of the proposed array antenna is compared with that of other state-of-the-art designs, which are summarized in Table 1. The dimension of the antenna in mm² is 495, which is smaller than the ⁴³⁾ and ⁴⁴⁾, that has 840 and 1482 mm². The proposed antenna also has resulted in better bandwidth compared to ³²⁻³⁴⁾. The gain of the antenna is better than that of the literature. The antenna also exhibits CP and LP radiation characteristics in different bands.

7. Conclusion

The article proposed a compact multi-band array antenna for millimeter-wave applications. The patch of the single-

element antenna has two orthogonal feeds with a phase difference of 150° to achieve CP characteristics in some bands. Consequently, the current flow in the circular patch is in the anti-clockwise direction, leading to LHCP characteristics at 28 GHz. Further, this antenna is arranged in series with eight elements along the y-axis and series-fed at the center. The center feed technique distributes the half power to the left and right elements, thereafter the power distribution decreases to the end element. This aided in achieving maximum antenna efficiency and reduced the reflection losses. Due to series fed and enhanced antenna aperture resulted in multiple resonances at 27, 28, 31.5, 34, and 37.2 GHz. The antenna demonstrated good bandwidth and gain. The array antenna has achieved broadside radiation with a broad beam in the XZ-plane, a narrow beam in the YZ-plane with LHCP radiation characteristics

at 28 GHz and 37.2 GHz, and LP characteristics at other bands. The antenna demonstrated good total efficiency with a high front-to-back ratio.

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